

#8

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

GOAL SETTING: BUILDING EMPATHY ONE-TO-ONE

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING CREATING ADDRESSING EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At all stages of a project/initiative, where a facilitator/actor wishes to understand the 'world views', challenges, experiences of another actor/ a stakeholder / a client.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>One-to-one, optionally extended to the whole group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>1-1.5 hrs</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials. Can be optionally conducted online.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 3, 9, 14, 15.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Understand the world-views, experiences, priorities and goals of actors/stakeholders who are unfamiliar to an actor/facilitator/innovation broker etc.
- Build empathy between actors so they can work together more effectively, drawing from each other's talents, knowledges, experiences etc.
- Incorporate empathetic understandings of each other to the interactive innovation process, as a result of increased awareness of each other's needs, motivations, goals etc. – and also each other's different forms of knowledge (and gaps).
- Establish a 'buddy system', where appropriate, where actors have a source of moral/empathetic support throughout the interactive innovation process.
- Use knowledge from using this tool to appraise how project/initiative activities are responding to the goals of different actors

Background and Logic

In multi-actor projects/initiatives, different actors (with different worldviews, experiences etc.) are not only challenged with working together on a common workplan, but they must actively 'mine' each other's differences. Actors' differences are the 'gold' of the interactive innovation process. Bringing together different forms of knowledge enriches the innovation process, which is why interactive forms of innovation are favoured.

Uncovering and appreciating each other's differences (roles, needs, motivations etc.) is an important part of the interactive innovation process (as pursued in Tools # 1-6). Building empathy and rapport between actors is also important to accommodate and nurture differences. If participating actors are not aware and appreciative of each other's differences, they may become invisible in the innovation process in favour of sameness & consensus. This forfeits the potential of interactive innovation.

This tool is used for actors to build empathy and rapport between them on a one-to-one basis. It can be used by participants working collaboratively on a project/initiative; between an innovation broker and his/her client; or between a farm advisor and his/her client. It is used to create understandings between actors of each other's world-views, circumstances, goals etc. Or, it can be used by a facilitator/innovation broker etc. to understand a client's/actor's world-views (in a one-way process). A record is kept of different actors' goals. This record is used to assess how relevant project/initiative activities are to diverse actors' goals¹.

Materials

- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- Images/pictures (randomly cut out from magazines)
- Camera/preferably a phone with a camera

¹ This tool is inspired by the Biographic Narrative Interpretive Method (BNIM) (Wengraf, 2001), which takes an open-ended approach to asking questions to elicit a narrative/story-like account of a person's life. This tool is adapted from a tool developed by Macken-Walsh et al., accessible [here](#).

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background of the one-to-one goal setting exercise, emphasising the need for actors to build empathy and understanding between each other.
- Issue the participating actors with their own copies of the purpose, logic and background document, comprising the steps of the exercise.
- For an facilitator/advisor/innovation broker working with an actor/client, and where the exercise is one way, explain that the facilitator etc. wishes to gain a better understanding of his/her client's circumstances & goals.

Step 2: 'Walk About'

- Actors may wish to visit each other's environment (such as a workplace/farm/other site of interest that's important to them and/or relevant to the project/initiative). Visiting a site of relevance brings conversation to life and allows actors to act as host, showing others insights to a place that is 'theirs'.
- Where such a visit is conducted, onn each occasion the conversation is focused on the person whose environment is being visited (actors may visit each other's environments, but the focus is always on the person whose environment is being visited)
 - » Where there are many themes/topics, ask participants 'do any of these go together and why?' (to cluster the theme/topics into manageable, distinctive themes).
 - » The actor who is seeking to understand more about the other (i.e. the visitor) asks,

Can you tell me the story about what this place means to you? (it is important that the listening actor doesn't interrupt, or ask questions, or offer advice. The listening actor should maintain a listening role. Clarifying questions may be asked after the whole story has been told, but the main aim is to listen!).

Are there any connections between this place and the project/initiative we are involved in? Or, for a facilitator/adviser/innovation broker - Are there any connections between this place and what my role could offer ?

Leaving our project/initiative/my role aside... What do you see for the future for this place?

What would you ideally like to see happen with this place in the future?

- The output from step two is that the actor whose environment is being visited feels that they have freely explained their history and their hopes. They have spoken uninterruptedly and feel that they have been listened to (and hopefully understood) by the visiting actor. The visiting actor feels enlightened about the actor they have just learned about and has a new appreciation of their circumstances.

Step 3: Goal Setting

- After the walk about, sit down – preferably in a room with tables and chairs.
- The visiting actor reiterates that they are now going to identify some goals, inspired by the walk-about they have just taken.
- A range of random images are spread out on either side of the table (cuttings from mainstream magazines, approx 15-20).
- The visiting actor asks,

'Considering the walk we've taken and all you've told me, what are your most important goals...?'

'If any picture here inspires anything, you can pick it up and leave it in front of you'

- Once the visited actor identifies a goal, it is written down on a post-it (either actor, preferably the visited actor) and placed beside any related image/s placed beside it.
- The whole range of goals are photographed by both participants, or photographed by one participant and shared with the other.
- The output of step 3 is a range of goals that have been identified by the visited actor. The visiting actor is aware of and understands their goals, and also knows the history, experiences, perspectives etc. that informs them.
- Steps 2 & 3 are repeated in reverse for the other participating actor.

Step 6: Use of Goal Setting Exercise to Support and Assess Interactive Innovation

- For goal setting exercises undertaken by a facilitator/ advisor/innovation broker:
 - » The pictured set of goals can be revisited at meetings, to assess how well project/initiative activities are responding to the achievement of those goals.
 - » Some facilitators may undertake the exercise with many or all members of a multi-actor group. The facilitator can examine all sets of goals to see how the goals inter-relate, coincide, possibly conflict with each other etc. This provides the facilitator with knowledge and sensitivity of likely dynamics within the group, and allows him/her to plan accordingly. S/he can also endeavour that goals are achieved across actor categories in a balanced way. The collection of different actors' goals provide a (benchmarking type) tool to assess if this is occurring.
- For goal setting exercises undertaken mutually between participants of a multi-actor group, empathy is created by the two participants involved. However, this empathy-making can be broadened to the wider multi-actor group, by presenting the outcomes to the wider group. A member of a pair may present the goals of the other to the wider group, or each person can present their own goals. Optionally, the group can be facilitated to examine the collection of all group members' goals, identifying synergies, conflicts and so on. This can assist in planning the nature of activities, avoiding overlaps and availing of opportunities to create collaborations in pursuing common goals. Similarly, conflicts may be avoided by discussions of how different goals may be pursued through different project activities.
- Overall, recorded goals (which may be updated by following Step 3, above), can be used to plan project activities and to assess how well project activities are meeting different actors' goals. Ensuring that all actors' goals are being responded to and avoiding some actors' goals being responded to more than others, is a central concern of interactive innovation processes.

